

Deliverable:

D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1

Data management plan

**Workpackage 1 of OH-
Harmony-Cap: Project
Coordination**

Responsible Partner: P13-SSI

Contributing partners: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA.

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1: Data Management Plan		
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Author	Nadia Boisen and Flemming Scheutz		
Other contributors			
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):		

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Background

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project, **Integrative Action-2.2, OH-HARMONY-CAP**: One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants

<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-oh-harmony-cap/>

OH-Harmony-CAP is a 2.5 year project which aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and support future studies of how best to detect and characterise food borne pathogens across the One Health sectors. The OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium comprises 15 One Health EJP partners.

Project Leader and DMP contact person: Nadia Boisen, P13-SSI, nbo@ssi.dk

Data Management Plan (DMP) is an important element of data management during a project as it is needed to continuously tracking, monitoring, analyseing and storing data in order to ensure progress throughout the project. Note, OH-Harmony-Cap is dedicated to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR-principle). Further, this data asset will be readily available for all our purposes, as well as those that may need this data in the future, also contributing to the sustainability of the project and its outcomes.

The specific deliverable will be a preliminary data management plan, which can be adjusted as the project progresses.

Process and format

The list of data covered in OH-Harmony-Cap DMP was specified during the first year of the project. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. Also, the management of the data is discussed proactively and the DMP is regularly discussed with the WP-leaders and with the OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium during the project.

This deliverable is the general description of the DMP. The DMP itself was compiled using a specific tool provided by the OHEJP: Collaborative Data Platform (DCP). Due to the delayed access of the tool the first version of the DMP was finished with minor delay, M33. OH-Harmony-Cap project Leader is responsible for the OH-Harmony-Cap DMP with contributions from task participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA.

The final DMP will be published at the end of the project lifetime.

First version of DMP (2020)

Four research datasets are listed in the first version of OH-Harmony-Cap DMP:

1. Questionnaire for WP2

“JIP-4-WP2_OHLABCAP_PILOTSURVEY_WP2-T2_SCORING_OF_COLLECTED_DATA_AND_CHOSEN_INDICATORS”

2. Questionnaire for WP3

“JIP-4-WP3_ONE_HEALTH_LABORATORY_INTEROPERABILITY_GUIDANCE._WP3-T1_SAMPLING_AND_TESTING”

3. Data collection for WP4

“JIP-4-WP4_HARMONISATION_OF_PROTOCOLS_WP4 T1_COLLECTION_OF_THE_LABORATORY_PROTOCOLS”

4. Data collecton for WP4

“JIP-4-WP4_HARMONISATION_OF_PROTOCOLS_WP4-T2_EVALUATION_OF_THE_COLLECTED_LABORATORY_PROTOCOLS”

The screenshot shows the 'Lisam ComplyStation' interface. The main content area displays a table of datasets under the heading 'Views overview'. The table has columns for Dataset ID, Category, Type of data, Species, Matrix, Description of d..., Contact, Dissemination, and Sustainability. There are four rows of data listed.

Dataset ID	Category	Type of data	Species	Matrix	Description of d...	Contact	Dissemination	Sustainability
JIP-4-2_WP2OHL...	Research data	Questionnaires	Not relevant	Not relevant	The purpose of th...	Flemming Scheut...	The final result wi...	2022-06-30
JIP-4-WP3_ONE_H...	Research data	Questionnaires	Not relevant	Not relevant	Establishing curre...	Declan Bolton, De...	The result of the f...	2020-12-31
JIP-4-WP4_HARM...	Research data	Data collection	Not relevant	Not relevant	Collection of the l...	Rosangela Tozzoli...	The result of the c...	2020-09-30
JIP-4-WP4_HARM...	Research data	Data collection	Not relevant	Not relevant	Evaluation of the l...	Karin Troell, karin...	The results will be...	2021-03-31